

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

2nd TNA Call Documentation - User

STORIES TNA2 POST RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Thermionic Energy Conversion receiver for STOring thermal energy and increasing electricity production
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	TECSTO
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	PROTEAS
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Thermionic; Engineered receiver; Thermal Battery; Static heat-to-electricity converter; Concentrated sunlight.
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	25/09/2023
Departure date (from town where RI located)	06/10/2023
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	26/09/2023
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	05/10/2023
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	2
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	Days of weekend (Saturday and Sunday)
Number of days using the RI	8
Number of users granted access (group size)	2
Comments	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
[Please	

The main objective of the project is to study the technical feasibility for installing thermionic energy converters (namely, TECs) in the PROTEAS facility to test two kinds of possible applications using concentrated sunlight:

case 1) - direct irradiation of the converter and connection with thermal storage system using heat transfer fluids for additional electricity production;

case 2) - irradiation of a sensible heat storage block (as a thermal battery) and thermal connection with the converter for storage&production-on-demand.

Both the scenarios require the achievement of high temperatures (> 1200 °C) for the practical operations. The project aims to demonstrate that such temperatures can be reached and to provide indications about size, geometry, and technical constraints for the future installation of TECs and the consequent experimental validation of the whole system.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

We performed simulation activities using the Free, Open-Source Software (FOSS) tool Tonatiuh++, which has been developed by members of the PROTEAS team (<https://github.com/CST-Modelling-Tools/TonatiuhPP/wiki>).

Additionally, we also used Autodesk Inventor and Comsol Multiphysics to perform a preliminary design and modelling of the thermionic receiver configuration under the concentrated sunlight at the conditions simulated by Tonatiuh++. Finally, analytical studies were prepared to understand the materials to be used as storage media, as well as a practical inspection of the room at the solar tower was made for understanding and accelerating the experimental phase in the near future.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

We found that the thermionic converter can act as engineered receiver and as new component for CSP/CST applications, and device for electricity production associated to a thermal battery. However, to reach the desired temperatures (> 1200 °C), secondary concentrators must be designed and applied to increase the input power density needed to the TEC. After the performed study at the TNA, we can release the following indications for the two identified cases:

Case 1

The technological feasibility of TEC integration with a thermal storage system was recently performed in July 2022 for the TECSAS project by the Users' group. The TEC anode was in contact with a storage system and able to exchange thermal energy with molten salts (NaNO₃/KNO₃/LiNO₃ 18%/45%/37% weight), that were pre-heated over the melting point at temperatures >120 °C. The specific composition was selected to have liquid phase at lower temperatures than usually used molten salts (>280 °C) to avoid problems of circuit block. However, conventional molten salts can be tested by increasing the TEC cathode temperature.

For this case, the PROTEAS facility will provide a perfectly controlled experimental platform for testing and evaluation of the thermionic receiver with two different demonstrator systems:

- Demonstrator 1: Integration into the solar tower system with molten salt thermal energy storage (TES) and operational power block

For this demonstrator configuration, the solar tower system of PROTEAS should be adapted to integrate the thermionic receiver. The latter will be sited on the second floor of the existing tower, which provides a test bed for testing of novel CST components, systems, and technologies. A special mounting frame will be designed and developed to host the receiver, and the necessary adaptations will be performed to the actual receiver according to the needs of the testing campaign. The existing piping of molten salt loop will be also adapted accordingly to integrate the

receiver with the TES tank, which currently has a nominal capacity of 1.6 MWh, carrying approximately 13 tons of molten salt. The existing power block, running on a closed-loop Rankine cycle (operated through the TES) will be also employed to demonstrate operation of the thermionic receiver into a complete solar tower system. Arranged on a sloped land, the heliostat field of the PROTEAS CST tower system currently consists of 50 tilt-roll rectangular heliostats (2.25 m x 2.25 m) of 5 m² each, yielding thus a combine mirror surface of 250 m². The capability of individually controlling each heliostat, enables the testing of the receiver at suitable fluxes in the range between 250 and 1000 suns. Preliminary Monte-Carlo ray-tracing simulations have been already performed, as shown in the following figure.

- Demonstrator 2: Integration into a CST parabolic dish system with molten salt thermal energy storage

The second possibility is to install the thermionic receiver into a parabolic dish by replacing the actual technology of Stirling engines. The PROTEAS facility actually hosts two parabolic dishes that are designed, built, operated, and tested by the company "Concentrated Systems Ltd". Each dish is equipped with a Stirling engine with a nominal power of 10 kWe, while the system also allows cogeneration of heat by effectively taking off the unused thermal energy and waste heat from the engine. The parabola of the dish (with a diameter of 8.5 m) is composed of segmented, specially shaped mirror facets, yielding approximately a raw concentrator surface of 58 m², while the geometric concentration ratio is 1150 with a focal length of 6 m. The very design of the steel structure of the parabola's frame enables great flexibility, scalability (e.g., 0.1 - 10 MWe), and modularity of the design. However, a totally new TES system based on molten salt circulation should be designed and developed and will be coupled to the receiver according to the needs of the experimental activities.

Case 2

A thermionic device can be included in thermal battery through the implementation of an innovative concept known as "dispatchable power wall" (DPW). This mechanism facilitates the transfer of heat from the storage block to the energy converter precisely when required. A CAD design is shown in the following figure to illustrate the concept. To that end, the thermal insulation of the storage block will incorporate openings on the top side, allowing radiant heat to escape.

During the storage period, the DPW will be strategically positioned to cover these openings, insulated with thermal insulation material. Conversely, during discharge, the DPW will shift to align with the heat concentrators, directing them towards the furnace openings. This configuration captures the heat radiated by the storage material and efficiently transfers it to the energy converters. Therefore, during the storage and charging phases of the battery, the DPW remains inactive, effectively retaining heat within the battery. During the discharge process, the activated DPW generates an exceptionally high heat flux through the converter, resulting in generation of a high-power density.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

The results obtained by the performed activities allowed to obtain an accurate design of the TEC receiver, as well as of thermal and optical accessory components, to be built for the installation in the PROTEAS facility.

Case 1

The converter will have an active area ranging from 15 to 30 cm to match the radiation field of the CSP plants to be used, is enclosed within the case and illuminated through a window made of a transparent material identified as fused silica (95% solar transmittance). A dedicated cooling system must possibly be designed and integrated to preserve the lifetime of the window and of its metal brazing. On the back side of the converter, the thermal coupling component has a primary importance since it will exchange efficiently heat from the thermionic anode to the downstream thermal system. A modular approach will be pursued for the TEC converter, that will be possibly divided in more modules electrically connected in series, to increase the output voltage and decrease the output current. Attention to the module's reproducibility will be put in order not to create bottlenecks for the output power. A step-up DC/DC converter circuit will be fabricated or purchased, as well as a circuit for biasing the converter at the maximum power (MPP) point.

A specific detailed and realistic modelling by Comsol derived the expected performance of TEC up to 1200 °C, where the radiative losses are moderate. By considering emitter and collector work-functions of 1.7 and 1.0 eV, respectively, a solar-to-electrical conversion efficiency > 32% for an incident solar power density of about 100 W/cm² (i.e., 1000 suns) and operating cathode temperature of about 1000 °C. The following figure describes well the efficiency realistically achievable by a solar TEC.

Case 2

In this case, the converter will be put in direct thermal contact with the storage block (in discharging phase) and the design for this converter is shown below. The presence of a heat concentrator is considered to maximize the heat flux onto the receiver with a limited size.

An essential aspect of designing these thermal batteries lies in selecting the appropriate storage media. Volumetric energy density and volumetric cost have been calculated for various thermal energy storage materials. These materials encompass latent heat storage (represented by red triangles) and sensible heat storage in both solids (blue dots) and liquids (green squares). The figure demonstrates that silicon and silicon alloys (e.g., FeSiB) exhibit exceptionally high latent heat and cost-effectiveness, rendering them ideal candidates as phase change materials for latent heat thermal batteries. Other solid materials, such as alumina (Al_2O_3), graphite, silicon carbide (SiC) and iron (Fe), boast notably high sensible heats and cost efficiency, making them ideal candidates for use in sensible heat thermal batteries. Notably, iron and silicon alloys also possess exceptional thermal conductivity, a crucial factor for efficient power extraction. This property ensures that heat can be delivered without creating excessive temperature gradients within the material, thereby preserving the exergy content of the extracted heat.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

The availability of cost-effective energy storage technologies with durations from 10 to 100 hours is crucial for enabling the widespread integration of variable renewable energy sources (VRES) like wind and solar energy into the electrical grid. In the recent years, several startups have emerged, focusing on developing solutions to store excess electricity in the form of heat at extremely high temperatures (>1200 °C). Notable examples include Rondo, Kraft Block, Alumina Energy, Antora Energy, and Thermal Battery Corp. Primarily, these companies are oriented toward thermal applications, aiming to directly fulfil the heat demand in industrial settings. Among these, only two companies, namely Antora Energy and Thermal Battery Corp. (both in USA), have integrated static thermal-to-electric energy converters into their systems. Both companies employ graphite blocks as the storage material, with the static energy converter featuring a thermophotovoltaic generator. Despite these companies have advertised very large investments (e.g., over 80 M\$ for Antora) to the best of our knowledge, a fully functional prototype incorporating these elements has not yet been produced, and the challenge of seamlessly integrating TPV technology into these advanced thermal batteries remains uncharted territory. Therefore, the simulation and modelling work performed in this project to define the way of using TEC as both topping cycle of conversion and device in the DPW concept open the path towards the demonstration of an advantageous technology in terms of low cost, scalability, and high conversion efficiency.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

No difficulties have been recorded.

Intended publications					
Simulations and modelling activities of the concepts studied in this project are aimed to be published in a peer-review journal between the next months. A tentative scheduling is January 2024 for the first submission, after a critical review of all the achieved results. The possible journals recognized as target for the publication are: Renewable Energy, Energies, Clean Technologies, Applied Thermal Engineering, Journal of Energy Storage or similar.					
Data management					
FAIR principles will be used regarding the data management as an agreement between the User group and the RI group. For the publication, open access will be guaranteed using the Open Science guidelines of the Users' Institution.					
Conclusions / additional comments					
Based on the activities of this work, a prototype will be built for performing an experimental campaign at the PROTEAS facility under next funded projects.					
Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS ? (necessary)					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction					
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments					
Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
An email after the submission as a receipt of the successful process should be guaranteed (not received in our case).					
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The procedure was clear but a summary of the different steps to be done could be a good option to be included in the context of the acceptance communication.					
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
No details are necessary.					

RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
No details are necessary.	
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
No details are necessary.	
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
No details are necessary.	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
No details are necessary.	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
No details are necessary.	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
No details are necessary.	
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
No details are necessary.	
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

No details are necessary.											
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
No details are necessary.											
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
No details are necessary.											
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Established channel with the RI team for future joint proposal/activities.											
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research											
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.											
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support											
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)							
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I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.

